

45. Responsible Tourism in Southeast Asia Post COVID-19 Pandemic using NVIVO

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EXTENDED ABSTRACT

The tourism industry is one of the sectors impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has caused a massive loss of income and unemployment worldwide. The pandemic has exacerbated the existing sustainability challenges of the tourism industry, challenges that are being addressed through responsible tourism. In this study, the authors examined and discussed responsible tourism based on literature, interviews, and blogs by using NVIVO software. The study identified several emerging themes from the software analysis based on eight interviews and three blog reviews. As a result, to practice responsible tourism requires the participation of all parties involved in the supply chain, including investors, institutions, governments, tour operators, local communities, and destination management organizations (DMOs) and the tourists themselves.

LITERATURE REVIEW

It is important to note that the tourism industry is based on people and target locations and the interactions between both. This industry is very sensitive to the micro and macro social and physical conditions of the destination environment (Hanafiah & Harun, 2010). The key element in the success of tourism development is tourism planners and other authorities involved in the tourism industry because they must pay attention to the views of the community about the development plan. Community involvement is critical to the success of tourism development and responsible tourism implementation and the attitudes of citizens can directly influence the development of the tourism industry (Ling et al., 2010).

Two years ago, the COVID-19 pandemic began wreaking unprecedented havoc on the tourism industry, resulting in massive loss of income and unemployment across the globe. Thus, the pandemic exacerbates the already existing sustainability challenges of the tourism industry (Seabra & Bhatt, 2022). The tourism industry in the Southeast Asia region has experienced several crises that raise questions about their ability to manage crises and readiness for future contingencies. The importance of these capabilities is increasing especially in today's landscape where the speed and scale of the COVID-19 pandemic threatens to derail the global economy (Eppang et al., 2020).

RESEARCH QUESTION

RQ1 What are the factors that influence implementation of responsible tourism (RT) in Southeast Asia (SEA)?

RQ2 How is environmental awareness related to RT in SEA?

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

RO1 To investigate the factors that influence the implementation of responsible tourism in (SEA)

RO2 To examine the relationship between environmental awareness and RT in (SEA)

RESEARCH METHOD

The study is qualitative in nature with the authors conducting a review of literature on responsible tourism, looking for factors that have been affecting development and implementation of responsible tourism. Based on the literature gathered, we performed coding using NVIVO software and classified the factors into significant themes such as environmental protection, community development, community-based tourist program and, lastly, environmental awareness. Questions were then developed based on these themes and used for interviews among respondents in SEA.

Figure 1: Flowchart for the Data Collection

These are some of the questions asked during the interviews with the respondents:

- Can you please describe what are the responsibilities of tourists when conducting tourism activities?
- What should a person do (not do) to be a responsible tourist?
- How would you differentiate responsibility from sustainability?
- Who are the key players in tourism industry?

- Who are the stakeholders involved in ensuring that tourism is sustainable?
- Can you please describe the way tourism can be developed sustainably?
- Can you provide examples/share your experience in relation to responsible tourism practices?
- Why is responsible tourism important today?

RESULT

Profiles/background of the Respondents

Out of eight respondents, six are female and the rest are male, most of them are considered as millennials, with ages ranging between 20-30 years old. Most of the respondents came from both Indonesia and Myanmar, with each country having three respondents plus they are officials and practitioners in the area of responsible tourism making them appropriate respondents for this study.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents

Variables	Descriptions	Total Number
Gender	Male	2
	Female	6
Age	20 – 30 years	5
	31 – 40 years	3
Country	Indonesia	3
	Malaysia	2
	Myanmar	3
Employment Status	Officials and Practitioners	5
	Students	1
	Frequent Travelers	2

DISCUSSIONS

Tourism is an industry that has continued to grow over the years. According to the World Tourism Organization, there are over one billion tourists who travel abroad each year, and this number is expected to grow. As the industry continues to grow, it becomes increasingly important for companies and governments to consider how their actions can affect the environment and communities.

Environmental Protection

In tourism, there are many ways in which people can be environmentally conscious. A few of these include using public transportation and walking instead of driving a car, recycling, avoiding the use of plastic bags and straws, buying locally made souvenirs instead of imported ones, and choosing to stay in hotels that are eco-friendly.

As one of the fastest growing industries in the world, tourism brings in billions of dollars every year and is a huge opportunity for many people to make a living. However, tourism also has its downsides. One of them being irresponsible tourism practices that cause damage to local communities, their culture and environment. To reduce these negative impacts on communities, responsible environmental tourism practices are needed.

Community Development

Developing tourism is not without its challenges. For the most part, developing tourism relies on the local people and their willingness to welcome tourists into their communities. This can present problems for some communities who may not be accustomed to foreigners or who are still struggling with poverty.

Responsible tourism development includes community development which focuses on the needs of the local community and ensures that they are benefitting from tourism activities taking place in their area. The goal is to empower them with skills, knowledge and opportunities so they can take advantage of the benefits that tourism can bring while protecting themselves from its negative impacts.

Figure 2: Development of Responsible Tourism

Community Based Tourist Program

Tourists often visit different places in the country to know more about the culture and traditions of that country. They are also able to see how people live their lives in a destination. Tourism can be good for the economy of a nation because it helps create jobs for locals. However, tourism can also have negative impacts on a country's development if not managed properly.

Environmental Awareness

Figure 3: How Environmental Awareness relates to Responsible Tourism

Environmental awareness tourism is a form of ecotourism that aims to raise people's awareness about the environment. It usually involves visiting natural landscapes and learning about their ecological significance. Environmental awareness tourism can be done in a variety of ways, including hiking, biking, kayaking, bird watching and more. The goal is to get people out into nature so they can understand how important it is to preserve it for future generations.

When it comes to sustainable tourism, the majority of people want to help the environment and do their part, but the movement is not always easy to define. The terms "green travel," "green tourism," "ecotourism," "responsible travel," "ethical tourism," and others may also come to mind. Reusing hotel towels for an additional day or choosing a reusable water bottle over single-use plastic bottles are just two examples of these concepts.

MANAGERIAL IMPLICATIONS

From the practitioners' perspective, this study provides invaluable inputs for policymaking, planning, destination management, collaborating, involving, and guiding stakeholders. The implication of this study is to perform critical stakeholders' perspectives for achieving long-term ecotourism sustainability through understanding stakeholders' responsibilities and roles in responsible tourism. This paper also emphasizes the importance of involving the local residents in the tourism destination, stakeholders that more often neglected in tourism development.

FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

A comparative study between the Southeast Asia countries (Malaysia, Indonesia, Philippines and Myanmar on Responsible Tourism can be conducted in the future using a similar methodology. The same study can be used as a baseline to see the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the responsible tourism industry in Southeast Asia after the post-pandemic.

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